

Establishment and maintenance of an Early Warning System in Ireland: A case study

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Abstract

Harmful Algal Bloom events can result in multiple effects and impacts on aquaculture and fishing operations, often resulting in socioeconomic losses, either through mortalities or temporary bans on the harvesting of product in aquaculture production areas. Many of these events give rise to food safety concerns, where marine biotoxins can accumulate within the tissues of filter feeding bi-valve molluscs above regulatory levels causing a variety of serious human illnesses if consumed. Many countries operate routine monitoring programmes for the detection of these events, where in recent years some countries have further expanded on these programmes to develop and establish Early Warning Systems to provide short term forecasting and prediction of the onset and duration of these events. From a stakeholder perspective, this leads to improved regulation, food safety and risk-based management decisions taken by the operator and regulator to minimise the economic and supply losses which are usually incurred of these events and ensuring the protection of the consumer. Ireland has been successfully operating such a system on a weekly frequency to all stakeholders and the public since 2013, by publishing a weekly bulletin which contain several collated data products from historical and current biotoxin and phytoplankton profiles, along with oceanographic in-situ satellite and modelled data products. These products and generated datasets are combined, where an expert evaluator reviews the data and provides a short-term forecast prediction (3-5 days).

Keywords: Early Warning Systems, Harmful Algal Blooms, prediction, forecasting, aquaculture
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Introduction

The Marine Institute, Ireland has been providing a weekly bulletin report to all stakeholders and the public since 2013. Ireland has a complex biotoxin profile in shellfish, multiple known toxigenic and ichthyotoxic phytoplankton species in its coastal waters and is often subject to large blooms resulting in water discolouration, foaming and mass mortalities of finfish, shellfish, and benthic invertebrates.

Large scale HAB events which occurred in Ireland during 2005-2007, resulting in multiple and prolonged closures in shellfish aquaculture production areas, and large-scale mass mortalities of finfish, prompted requests from stakeholders, in particular the aquaculture industry for the provision of an Early Warning System (EWS) to be implemented. Through the ASIMUTH project (Applied simulations and Integrated modelling for the understanding of toxic and harmful algal blooms) this allowed for the approach, stakeholder consultation process, design, and development of a prototype EWS to be implemented. Through successive funding projects, Ireland's EWS has been further enhanced over the years, and is detailed in this case study.

Early Warning System Case Study–Ireland's Experience

Through rigorous, robust, and intensive monitoring programmes over a 40-year period, we have identified the presence and regular occurrence of four main marine biotoxin groups in Ireland; Diarrhetic Shellfish Toxins (DST); Amnesic Shellfish Toxins (AST); Azaspiracids (AZA) and Paralytic

Shellfish Toxins (PST). The occurrence of causative toxigenic plankton species in the water column and their associated Harmful Algal Bloom (HAB) events are a regular occurrence, often resulting in long periods of closure for harvesting in production areas, and occasionally responsible for the mortalities of farmed finfish and wild fish, shellfish, and benthic invertebrates.

Information about the stakeholders—who was impacted and were needs identified?

From the mid to late 1990's, there were a number of reported illnesses following the consumption of shellfish exported from Ireland. The development and expansion of the aquaculture industry was constrained by the multiple and long periods of closures prohibiting harvesting and product recalls. This contributed to a review and overhaul of the monitoring programme by affected stakeholders. The main stakeholders who were and continue to still be impacted HAB events can be categorised into the following four main groups; Industry; Regulators; Health and Society. The identified requirements and needs of these four groups of an EWS system overlap with each other.

Industry—commercial Food Business Operators (FBO) of shellfish and finfish licensed aquaculture operations in classified production areas. Fishermen and fishing vessels for pelagic and demersal fishing, and the dredging of shellfish i.e., scallop (*Pectinidae*) and razor clam (*Ensis*) species from offshore areas. Identified needs of an EWS for this group included the early notification and predictive forecasting of the probability of a HAB event occurring (short

term 3–5-day forecast) with the forecast to be presented in a visual, understandable, and interpretable format accessed through a user-friendly platform.

Regulatory–Competent Authorities including enforcement; licensing; movement of products, and legislative agencies. National reference laboratories and approved monitoring laboratories. Other national agencies include those with a remit covering natural resources (i.e., water), and food security. Identified needs of an EWS for this group included the predictive forecasting of the onset and duration of a HAB event and its spatial extent, and to support and supplement the scientific advice presented to regulatory agencies and authorities.

Health–Public and private health bodies, and agencies with a remit in the management of water quality and food security. Identified needs of an EWS for this group include the communication of alerts and data on toxin concentrations from HAB events and their associated potential impacts on human health and related illnesses.

The society (individuals and communities), particularly regarding prevention and protection of public health. Identified needs of an EWS for this group included the publication and dissemination of alerts of HAB events and blooms occurring in recreational settings, i.e., beaches and water bodies used for water sports, diving, and swimming.

Developmental and monitoring status in Ireland

Ireland established routine phytoplankton monitoring in the 1980s for the identification and enumeration of toxigenic species

known to cause human illnesses through the consumption of toxin contaminated shellfish. This was the first important step to compile and understand the complexity of the biotoxin profile in Irish coastal waters. This monitoring expanded with the growth of the aquaculture industry to include shellfish monitoring in the 1990's for the presence/absence of biotoxins by bioassay, whilst in the 2000's chemical monitoring for the discrimination and quantification of biotoxin compounds was implemented.

Presently, Ireland has a widely distributed and varied aquaculture industry, with approximately 100 classified production areas harvesting blue mussel (*Mytilus edulis*), pacific oyster (*Crassostrea gigas*), native oyster (*Ostrea edulis*), clam (*Ruditapes*, *Venerupis*, *Ensis* species), common cockle (*Cerastoderma edule*) and King scallop (*Pecten maximus*).

The routine phytoplankton monitoring programme includes full community analysis (species identification and enumeration) on a weekly frequency from all actively harvesting production areas. The biotoxin monitoring programmes analyse all shellfish species from active production areas, where the frequency is weekly for *Mytilus edulis*, fortnightly for *Pecten maximus* and monthly for all other species. The frequency is increased accordingly if a potential risk is observed, including time of year, toxicity in adjacent areas or in other shellfish species and the presence/increase of the toxigenic phytoplankton species.

In 2020, the total value of the Irish Seafood sector was €526 million (m) with a total volume of 290,400 tonnes (t). This breaks

down to €346m (252,400t) of sea-caught fish; €129m (14,000t) of farmed finfish and €51m (24,000t) of farmed shellfish (BIM, 2021).

Due to the frequent occurrence of HAB events impacting on harvesting regimes and commercial operations, a requirement was identified by stakeholders for an early warning system (EWS) to forecast the onset of HAB events to assist risk management decision making at industry/FBO/regulator level.

Approaches and technologies adopted in implementing an EWS

The Irish EWS comprises of Weekly HAB report/bulletin, which is compiled and published by the Irish Marine Institute as an assistance information tool to industry. These weekly 12-page bulletins contain a number of collated data products from historical and current biotoxin and phytoplankton profiles, along with oceanographic in-situ and modelled data products used as a predictive forecasting tool. An expert evaluator reviews the data and provides a short term 3–5 day forecast prediction (Fig. 1.).

Fig. 1. Example of the front page of the Irish weekly bulletin detailing the short-term predictions and risk for the week. *AHAB bulletin*

The generation and publication of the weekly HABs Bulletin is an eight-step process (Fig. 2.).

1. *In situ* HAB and Biotoxin Data Products– collates the current and historical results from the phytoplankton and biotoxin monitoring programmes from the Marine Institutes SQL server database, HABs2, presented as spatio-temporal scatter and donut plots
2. Phytoplankton Data Products– generates a report of the top five most abundant phytoplankton taxa in cells L⁻¹ per coastal region for the week previous.
3. Satellite– generates daily maps which present large spatial scale information on surface phytoplankton blooms (Chl *a*) and sea surface temperature.
4. Calculate Chlorophyll and Sea Surface Temperature Anomalies–generates a series of daily images of the current weekly conditions of chlorophyll and sea surface temperatures.
5. *In-situ* weather buoys– data collated by the Irish weather buoy network used to create a ten-year SST for the week in analysis.
6. Modelled Data Products– generates particle tracking imagery at three depths and three-day predictive hydrodynamics (estimated water flows at the mouth and mid-bay sections) for three bays of interest.
7. Data Evaluation and Prediction– text prediction with rationale, based on interpretation of all available data by an expert evaluator, is presented. The rationale is based on available scientific data, potential driving factors and experience.

- Publication—a .pdf of the current bulletin is uploaded to the Marine Institute’s HABs website <https://webapps.marine.ie/habs>

Description of EWS implemented and the communications and interactions with stakeholders

Ireland’s EWS provides valuable information to assist and inform its stakeholders. The focus is to provide information to facilitate rapid decision making prior to the onset of a HAB event. These decisions can include increased

harvesting prior to closures in affected areas, movement, and transfer of caged finfish away from high biomass blooms, and other measures to mitigate or minimise losses. Interactions and feedback from stakeholders are requested on a regular basis. Ideas and novel technologies are often explored to provide additional information and further accuracy to prediction and forecasting. Stakeholder feedback has also been sought through surveys and questionnaires since its implementation in 2013 to continuously assess the EWS is fit for purpose.

Fig. 2. An overview of the process to generate and publish a weekly HAB bulletin (Leadbeatter *et al.*, 2018).

Results in terms of forecast operations

To measure how accurate and successful the forecast bulletins are in their weekly predictions and alerts, two separate evaluation exercises were conducted. During the ASIMUTH project (Applied simulations and Integrated modelling for the understanding of toxic and harmful algal blooms) the estimation of success was through assessing an assigned score if the toxin concentrations observed were above or below regulatory levels during a 16-week period for each biotoxin group. Overall, the success of prediction was calculated at approximately 80% (Maguire *et al.*, 2016)

Through the PRIMROSE project (Predicting the impact of regional scale events on the aquaculture sector). A different method was applied to calculate the success rate of forecasting prediction and accuracy, by comparing the published prediction of a current week and if the predicted area was closed the following week due to biotoxin concentrations above regulatory levels. An overall success rate of 87.25% was calculated for a 17-week period during 2020, where it was observed that incorrect predictions were always due to overestimating the risk of a HAB event occurrence. Therefore, all HAB event occurrences over this period were predicted.

Consequences of EWS on stakeholder requirements

The EWS products which have been developed fulfil the requirements of the four identified groups of stakeholders; Industry; Regulators; Health and Society. These developed end products include *in-situ* HAB and biotoxin products, remote sensing satellite products, regional oceanic modelling systems detailing

the hydrodynamic processes into and out of specific bays including particle tracking at the mouth and mid-sections of water bodies. These products when combined are designed to meet the requirements and is achieved by the outputs of industry—reduce mortalities, minimise against financial loss and improve supply demand logistical chains. The output here is for profitability, expansion, and production of safe seafood products.

Regulators—ensuring food safety and the protection of the consumer is enforced by taking the necessary actions, development of strategies minimising economic losses and impacts on the environment. The main output is that monitoring and prediction through EWSs ensures safe seafood on the market.

Health—protecting human health ensuring only safe product is on the market for human consumption and ensuring water quality is to a high standard. This translates into the output of reducing the number of human illnesses occurring and reported from HAB events.

Society—forecasting of blooms which may impact on leisure activities, water sports and swimming. The output for this group also results in reducing the number of human illnesses occurring and reported from HAB events and reducing environmental impacts.

Lessons learned

When establishing and implementing an EWS in Ireland there has been several valuable lessons learned and actioned in a bid to continually improve the service:

- a. It is critically important to have an in-depth knowledge and understanding of the country/region toxicity profile, which can

- vary from region to region.
- b. With this understanding, the designed monitoring programmes should be fit for purpose so all HAB events of all types can be captured by in-situ observations, modelling and remote sensing monitoring programmes and tools.
 - c. For the generation of fluid weekly bulletins without delays, it is vital that all datasets used in the compilation and generation of the bulletin are reliable (quality control checks to ensure integrity) and available.
 - d. That all aspects of the bulletin generation and publication are continuously reviewed and evaluated to ensure they continue to be fit for purpose and of relevance to the stakeholders.
 - e. As part of the above review and evaluation, it is necessary to continue to liaise, listen and work with stakeholders ensuring their requirements are continuously met and delivered.
 - f. Data disruption due to downtimes are minimised and mitigated against, and that detailed procedures are in place to cover hardware and software upgrades, backup, and disaster recovery.
 - g. Financial support, in addition to having the appropriate human and technical resources, is critical for the ongoing maintenance and improvements of established working EWSs.
 - h. Ongoing stakeholder support and commitment is continuously required for EWS success, especially from end users and those who make risk based operational decisions on the forecast predictions, particularly industry and regulators.

The success of any implemented EWS in a region is due to a combination of the above, and to the system's capacity and ability to

evolve and improve over time to incorporate new technologies, data streams, modelling and in-situ monitoring. The established EWS should not be a static process, but a system which can evolve and keep pace with stakeholder requirements.

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